

IMPROVING THE DIRECTIONS OF ATTRACTING FOREIGN INVESTMENT IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY

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Annotation: *The article covered the flow, composition and dynamics of direct foreign investments, as well as the practice of attracting them to the economy of Uzbekistan and improving it. There is discussed impact of foreign investment to economic growth, the role of foreign investments in economic growth in Uzbekistan, the role of foreign investment in Uzbekistan, the importance of foreign investment in economic achievement, the role of foreign investments in fixed capital and the ICOR index, analyzed. The current problems related to the attraction and use of foreign investments in the country are studied and tasks to be addressed are considered.*

Key words: *investments, foreign investments, the economic growth, JDP, investment projects, tax credits, index ICOR, directs foreign investment.*

Introduction: Foreign investments are all the property, financial, and intellectual assets that are mobilized by foreign investors for business and other activities of the economy of another state in order to obtain a high level of income and efficiency. Foreign investment is a source of external financing, unlike domestic investment. Foreign investments differ from domestic investments in that the investor is a citizen of another country. According to their economic content, foreign investments are divided into debt capital (i.e. debt and credit), and direct and portfolio investments. The direction of investments determines which type of foreign investment they fall into.

Systematic expansion of cooperation with international financial institutions, attraction of long-term investment loans and direct foreign investments occupy a leading place in the program of anti-crisis measures in Uzbekistan.

Foreign investments can take part in joint ventures, create enterprises fully owned by foreign investors, participate in privatization, establish a bank with foreign partners, purchase securities, have the right to use land and other natural resources, and operate in free economic zones.

Foreign investments are mainly influenced by 2 groups of factors:

1) economic factors:

- production development and economic growth rates are maintained at the same rate;
- implementation of deep structural changes in the economy of the world and individual countries (in particular, under the influence of scientific and technical progress and the development of the world services market);
- deepening of international specialization and cooperation of production;
- growing transnationalization of the world economy (the volume of production of foreign branches of Transnational Corporations (TCCs) of the United States of America is 4 times greater than the export of goods from the United States);
- internationalization of production and deepening of integration processes;
- active development of international economic relations (IRI) and others.

2) political factors:

- liberalization of capital export (import) (free economic zones, offshore areas, etc.);
- conducting industrialization policy in developing countries;
- carrying out economic reforms (privatization of state enterprises, support of the private sector and small business);

- carrying out a policy of keeping the level of employment, etc.

All types of tangible and intangible assets and rights related to them, including intellectual property rights, which foreign investors add to business activities and other types of activity objects mainly for the purpose of obtaining income (profit), any income received from foreign investments are considered foreign investments in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

This, in turn, made it possible to develop a large-scale complex program of anti-crisis measures aimed not only at mitigating the negative consequences of the crisis, but also at turning the economy of Uzbekistan into a stronger and more durable economy, and its faster implementation. The most crucial task in this regard is to fundamentally modernize the production base of the economy, to re-equip it technically and technologically, in exchange for attracting foreign investments and long-term investment loans.

Therefore, since investments are the power that moves any economy and ensures its development, we should use all our possibilities to increase the amount of investments directed to our economy.

As we see, there are a number of problems in our republic, and we believe that the following measures should be taken to solve them:

- creation of equal opportunities and benefits for foreign investors and national producers;
- bringing national accounting closer to International Financial Accounting Standards;
- acceleration of activities of joint ventures directed to foreign markets, stabilization of currency flow. Achieving this through partial exemption from various communal services and full exemption from taxes, levies, customs fees;
- in order to prevent regional one-sidedness of investments, to divide the regions into 3 groups according to the level of development, to create more interest and inclination for investors to the less developed regions;
- study the practice of free export zones and achieve their implementation in our country.

In 2019, it was developed on the implementation of important projects aimed at modernization, technical and technological re-equipment. For the implementation of investment projects within the framework of the program approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 29, 2019, it was planned to attract loans and investments in the total amount of more than 22 billion dollars from international financial organizations, bilateral agreements and leading foreign companies. Currently, specific sources of investment and financing of more than 80 projects with a total value of more than 19 billion dollars have been identified and agreements have been signed with foreign partners.

Generally speaking, in the conditions of the world financial and economic crisis, the basis of the successful and stable development of the economy of Uzbekistan is a unique and suitable model of economic reforms, which are deeply thought out and fully take into account the peculiarities of Uzbekistan. The consistent implementation of this program over the past 18 years is a serious formal factor that leads to continuous high-speed economic growth of agrarian, low-tech and inefficient economic structure, which is fully connected to the former "Center", entering the diversified world market with a wide variety of competitive finished products and ensure that it becomes a modern economy with an impeccable credit history.

Conclusion: In conclusion, it should be said that the future development of Uzbekistan and the world economy implies that today almost every specialist and business entity has realized that it depends on investments. It is not difficult to understand

that the wider attraction of investments, especially foreign investments, to the economy of our republic today is due to the fact that they have become an important basis for ensuring the effective implementation of economic reforms carried out in our country.

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